

GENDER ASPECTS OF ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGY

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Abstract: In the field of world linguistics, determining the expression of national-cultural and gender characteristics is considered one of the important tasks, and this article is devoted to the gender aspect of the research of English phraseology.

Key words: language, discourse, gender, phraseology, linguistics, grammar, style.

Gender studies of linguistic units (phraseology), the use of linguistic means in terms of one or another gender, as well as determining the expression of national-cultural and gender characteristics in languages are an important task facing linguists around the world.

Language is an important source of information. We must learn to carefully treat our classical and modern cultural values, which have opened the door to great opportunities for the general population. In addition, with the development of international economic and cultural ties between Uzbekistan and the countries of the world, interest in learning foreign languages is also growing. In recent years, a comprehensive system of teaching foreign languages, especially English, has been created and is being widely implemented in order to ensure deeper integration of our country into the world community.

The study of gender characteristics of phraseological units is relevant, since the features of representatives of one or another gender in the use of linguistic means and cultural and social factors have their own characteristics, and these aspects are important for the correct organization of communication. It is important to study the process of gender conceptualization, identify the main levels and components that form gender concepts, determine the factors and parameters that create them, highlight national-cultural, etymological, historical features. Also, one of the important problems is a comparative study of male and female stereotypes in the imagination of the phraseological world of the English language, determining gender asymmetry and connotations in them. The results of such a study can serve as a basis for a lexicographic description of gender phraseological units of the English language and their adequate interpretation in contexts.

Gender is not a linguistic concept, its content can be clarified by analyzing the language structure, which requires studying the cultural characteristics of gender from a linguistic point of view. Taking into account the increasing number of studies by linguists, sociologists, psychologists and philosophers, we can talk about the development of cognitive phraseology. The term "cognitive phraseology" was first introduced into science by Russian linguists, their methodological and linguistic foundations were determined. Within the framework of cognitive idioms, such opportunities as identifying national phraseological concepts, comparing the mental spaces of carriers of certain cultures, studying the mechanisms of changing emotional-mental categories in the language structure, studying the mental meaning of idioms are opened. one or another language is defined. In this process, it was proven that the cognitive nature of phraseological units, one or another phenomenon does not simply name the object, but expresses the connection, the information that constitutes the content of phraseological units.

The following phraseological units representing social norms, social relations and social roles can be included in social and everyday knowledge: *cut somebody off with a shilling; good wine needs no bush; rob Peter to pay Paul; sit above the salt; sit below the salt* and others.

There is a huge stock of religious knowledge in the content structure of phraseological units: *cast the first stone at somebody; The best of British luck to you! The three tailors of Tooley Street.*

The process of metaphorization is based on the axiological way of being, since "the most fundamental values of a culture are consistent with the metaphorical structure of the main concepts of this culture." Metaphorization is one of the ways to create emotional-evaluative phraseological content, as well as a means of expressing the connection between the cognitive activity of English speakers and their national and cultural characteristics. Figurative-metaphorical perception of unvariant combinations is an important source that enriches the phraseology of any language, including English. Many metaphorical expressions are euphemistic in nature, as a result of which one or another concept is implicitly expressed.

Metonymic movements are based on various forms of kinship:

- a body part is used in place of the function it performs: *long ears;*
- this or that person's name in place of the things associated with them: *Big Bertha;*
- the name of the street on which the institution is located, or the name of the people associated with it: *Downing Street; Fleet Street;*

Phraseologisms in which the name of a part is used instead of the whole: *beer and skittles; the butcher, the baker, the candlestick-maker*.

There are biological and social interpretations of the roles and relationships of men and women in society, which are called gender stereotypes. The term stereotype is interpreted as part of the environment, a certain "image", a mental "picture" recorded as a result of the reflection in the consciousness of a person of a "model" fragment of the real world, a certain invariant of the world. existence, existing in a certain region. Gender stereotypes consist of the opinions of representatives of both sexes about culturally and socially conditioned qualities, signs and norms of activity and their manifestation in language. Stereotypes in one form or another affect any person.

Thus, it can be concluded that the key to understanding stereotypes is the task of responsibility for the transmission to generations of information that is preserved in the public consciousness of a particular ethnic group and expresses cultural values and traditions in language.

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